

**Enamel Micro-Cracks Characteristics Before and After Debonding of Ceramic
Brackets; An in Vitro Study**

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ABSTRACT:

Objective:

To evaluate and compare the mean width of enamel micro-cracks on extracted tooth of adult patients before and after removal of ceramic brackets.

Patients and Methods:

A total number of 50 extracted human teeth were included in this study. and stored at room temperature (37°C) in distilled water. The buccal enamel surface was evaluated under scanning electron microscope (SEM;Hitachi TM-1000, Tokyo, Japan) operated at 15 kV, at less than 5×10^{-2} Pa (electron gun vacuum) and at approximately 30 – 50 Pa (specimen chamber vacuum). The buccal enamel surface was divided in three zones of equal height (first zone-cervical third, second zone-middle third, and third zone-occlusal third) for detailed mapping of enamel micro-cracks. For all the teeth, the width, and location (cervical, middle, and occlusal third) of the longest enamel micro-crack was measured before and after removal of ceramic brackets.

Results:

Mean width of micro-cracks after debonding was 11.29 ± 2.99 μm as compared to the before debonding value of 8.03 ± 2.30 μm (p-value <0.0001). In zone 1, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was 7.95 ± 2.19 μm and after debonding was 11.29 ± 2.99 μm (p-value <0.0001). In zone 2, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was 7.56 ± 2.16 μm and after debonding was 11.30 ± 3.17 μm (p-Value 0.01). In zone 3, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was 8.76 ± 2.71 μm versus 11.05 ± 3.28 μm (p-value <0.0001).

Conclusion:

Debonding of ceramic brackets significantly increases the width of enamel micro-cracks. In present study mean width of enamel micro-cracks before debonding was $7.95 \pm 2.19 \mu\text{m}$ and it was increased to $11.29 \pm 2.99 \mu\text{m}$ after debonding.

Keywords: Enamel micro-cracks, ceramic brackets, debonding.

INTRODUCTION:

With the introduction of acid-etch bonding technology, the direct bonding of brackets became the procedure of choice in orthodontic treatment. The debonding of brackets is a procedure with risk of damage to the enamel in the form of cracks, scratches or tissue loss. The formation of enamel micro-cracks and fractures is one of the biggest concerns of people wearing fixed orthodontic appliances. It is proved by many studies that micro-cracks, which can develop during removal of brackets at the end of the treatment,¹⁻⁵ may jeopardize the integrity of the enamel, causing stain and plaque accumulation on the rough fractured surface. That might increase susceptibility to carious lesions and detracts from the appearance of the teeth.⁶⁻⁸

The concern for enamel damage is especially critical when debonding ceramic brackets. Ceramic brackets were introduced to orthodontics to meet the increasing demand for more esthetic appliances. In recent years, the number of adults seeking orthodontic treatment has increased, and the need for more esthetic appliances has led manufacturers to design various types of ceramic brackets. Ceramic brackets are made up of poly crystalline material and aesthetically more pleasing. The physical properties of ceramics such as hardness, high bond strength, and low fracture toughness or brittleness have led to many reports of enamel surface damage during the removal procedure.⁹

The key to preservation of this tissue is the use of techniques that prevent the development of adhesive failures at the enamel-adhesive interface,^{10,11} leaving as much adhesive on the tooth surface as possible.¹² Maximum preservation of enamel surface structure after orthodontic treatment with minimum enamel loss during bracket

debonding and polishing is one of the goals of orthodontists.^{3,5,10,13} Techniques that promote the union failure at the bracket-adhesive interface are most appropriated, because the adhesive remnant minimizes the risk of enamel loss during debonding.^{2,14,15}

Orthodontic treatment may be performed for adult patients whose enamel has higher elastic modulus(resistance to being deformed elastically) and hardness at the tooth's surface than that from young people ¹⁰.These properties of the enamel might correlate to the fracture toughness and brittleness ¹⁶.Thus, the question about the effect of debonding on existing micro-cracks or formation of new ones in teeth of adult patients arises.

In literature, knowledge exist on enamel microcracks evaluation after debonding but very few studies have been done on enamel surface evaluation before bonding.

As the demand of more aesthetic orthodontic treatment is increasing day by day, patients are more concern about enamel damage. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the surface characteristics of micro cracks before and after removal of ceramic brackets.

Methods:

A total number of 50 extracted human teeth were included in this study. and stored at room temperature (37°C) in distilled water. The buccal enamel surface was evaluated under scanning electron microscope (SEM;Hitachi TM-1000, Tokyo, Japan) operated at 15 kV, at less than 5×10^{-2} Pa (electron gun vacuum) and at approximately 30 – 50 Pa (specimen chamber vacuum).

Buccal enamel surface of extracted premolar teeth was divided into three zones (1st zone-cervical third, 2nd zone-middle third, 3rd zone-incisal third). Linear defects on enamel surface measured under scanning electron microscope operated at 15 kV, at less than 5×10^{-2} Pa (electron gun vacuum) and at approximately 30 –50 Pa (specimen chamber vacuum).

Every zone (upper, middle, lower) was divided into 10 measurement areas using a ruler. A total of 30 measurement areas were obtained. A measurement step (the distance between the two measurement areas) was quantified as follows; $X=h/30$ where X =measurement, h =vertical height of tooth's crown. The width of the longest micro-crack was evaluated in the same segment before and after debonding in spite of the changes in the length of micro-crack.

Orthodontic tool that hold the arch-wire on a tooth. (Clarity; 3M Unitek, Monrovia, Calif) in all tooth procedures.

All bonded ceramic brackets were removed with the conventional Utility (Dentaurum) pliers by hand [debonding method is based on the methodology of other study (B ishara et al. 2008)]. The mesio–distal edges of the bracket wings were squeezed gently until

the bracket is removed. After debonding, all visible residual adhesive was removed using a slow-speed hand piece and a carbide finishing bur. The enamel surface was reevaluated with SEM as described earlier.

RESULTS:

Regarding zone of micro-cracks before debonding majority of micro-cracks were in zone 1, 19 (38%), 17 (34%) in zone 2 and 14 (28%) in zone 3.

Mean width of micro-cracks after debonding was significantly high as compared to before debonding. Mean width of micro-cracks after debonding was $11.29 \pm 2.99 \mu\text{m}$ as compared to the before debonding value of $8.03 \pm 2.30 \mu\text{m}$ (p-value < 0.0001).

On comparison of width of micro-cracks according to location of cracks, In zone 1, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was $7.95 \pm 2.19 \mu\text{m}$ and after debonding was $11.29 \pm 2.99 \mu\text{m}$ (p-value < 0.0001). In zone 2, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was $7.56 \pm 2.16 \mu\text{m}$ and after debonding was $11.30 \pm 3.17 \mu\text{m}$ (p-Value 0.01). In zone 3, mean width of micro-cracks before debonding was $8.76 \pm 2.71 \mu\text{m}$ versus $11.05 \pm 3.28 \mu\text{m}$ (p-value < 0.0001) (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of Width of Micro-Cracks Before and After Debonding.

Enamel Micro-cracks (μm)	Before Debonding	After Debonding	P-Value
In All Zones			
Mean	8.03	11.29	<0.0001
S.D.	2.30	2.99	
Zone One			
Mean	7.95	11.41	<0.0001
S.D.	2.19	2.90	
Zone Two			
Mean	7.56	11.30	0.01
S.D.	2.16	3.17	
Zone Three			
Mean	8.75	11.05	<0.0001
S.D.	2.69	3.28	

DISCUSSION:

In the treatment of adult patients, the addition of esthetic brackets was a much-celebrated event. It has been accepted by adults which has expanded the development of contemporary orthodontic modalities. Since their advent, progressive improvements in product design have been noted which has resulted in the superior performance of ceramic brackets.

Damage to the enamel occurring due to the removal of ceramic brackets has been the concern to many researchers and has a number of studies. Some of these studies have evaluated many factors related to bonding procedure such as the etching time and the type of resin adhesive used.^{17,18} Some have assessed the types of bracket bases, having different groove designs or mechanism for retentions of the bonding agents. Many studies evaluated bonding method, bonding material or combination of both.¹⁹

In this study, we evaluated the enamel damage in terms of micro-cracks after removal of ceramic brackets. In present study, Mean width of micro-cracks after debonding was $11.29 \pm 2.99 \mu\text{m}$ as compared to the before debonding value of $8.03 \pm 2.30 \mu\text{m}$.

A study conducted by Namdhari et al. conducted a study on width of enamel micro-cracks after debonding of ceramic brackets from different manufacturers, the authors reported mean width of micro-cracks $13.0 \mu\text{m}$, $10.8 \mu\text{m}$, and $17.16 \mu\text{m}$ from samples of different teeth of different patients. the authors only evaluated 3 teeth in their study.²⁰

Dumbryte et al. in 2013 conducted a study on width of microcracks before bonding and after removal of metal brackets on 45 extracted human teeth. They divided the tooth surface in three zones from cervical to incisal area. The width of microcracks were

measured in first, second and third zones were $5.69 \pm 11.26 \mu\text{m}$, $7.71 \pm 8.91 \mu\text{m}$ and $3.34 \pm 12.36 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. While the overall measured length of microcracks was $7.75 \pm 4.37 \mu\text{m}$.²¹

CONCLUSION:

Debonding of ceramic brackets significantly increases the width of enamel micro-cracks. In present study mean width of enamel micro-cracks before debonding was $8.01 \pm 2.34 \mu\text{m}$ and it was increased to $11.27 \pm 2.34 \mu\text{m}$ after debonding.

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